

Investigation for carbon/carbon composite made from single-walled carbon nanotube (SWNT) buckypaper/pitch

Nam-Gun Yun
Agency for Defense Development
Yuseong P.O.Box35, Daejeon 305-600, S.KOREA
ngyun@add.re.kr

and

Seung-Goo Lee
BK21 FTIT, Chungnam National University
220 Gung-dong Yuseong-gu, Daejeon 305-764, S.KOREA
lsgoo@cnu.ac.kr

SUMMARY

Carbon/carbon composite used single walled carbon nanotube (SWNT) buckypaper as reinforcement material and pitch as matrix was developed. Pitch was impregnated into buckypaper using toluene and drying, stabilization, carbonization process was performed in sequence. Carbonization was repeated to increase pitch contents and density of carbon/carbon composite up to 3 times. Voids in carbon/carbon composite were decreased as increase the repeat number of carbonization. Electrical conductivity and density was remarkably increased with carbonization and saturated at 2nd carbonized specimens. These results show that discontinuity of SWNT at buckypaper was overcome by carbonization process and nanotubes can be used as reinforcement materials for carbon/carbon composite.

Keywords: SWNT, buckypaper, carbon/carbon, conductivity, composite

INTRODUCTION

A SWNT have exceptionally high electrical conductivity and mechanical property. For example, electrical conductivity of SWNT could be as high as 2×10^5 S/cm at room temperature and tensile strength could be 500 GPa. It has been regarded that SWNT is the most hopeful reinforcement materials for multifunctional nanocomposites [1]. Several approaches to apply SWNT for new nanocomposites were performed by many researchers. But generally if apply SWNTs at multiscale nanocomposite by mixing or casting methods, it was very hard to get uniform dispersion of SWNTs because they have a strong tendency to form bundles and to aggregate together. To get uniform properties of SWNTs reinforced nanocomposites, High Performance Materials Institute (HPMI) in Florida state university developed SWNT membrane (called buckypaper) as a uniform reinforcement material for nanocomposites [2-3]. Available experimental results provided that buckypaper reinforced nanocomposites have good compatibility between nanotube and resin, high nanotube loading (as high as 60 wt% compared to the directly mixing process of 5 ~ 10 wt% SWNT loading). Considerable improvements in quality and properties of the nanocomposites can be obtained through using buckypapers and buckypaper-based nanocomposites are very promising for next generation high performance composites.

The aim of this paper is development of new carbon/carbon composite and increasing electrical conductivity of buckypaper using a randomly oriented SWNT buckypaper as reinforcement material and a mesophase pitch as matrix [4-7]. To have high density and low voids in carbon/carbon composite, we repeated impregnation and carbonization process up to 3 times.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Buckypaper is thin (10~30 μ m) membrane of nanotube networks produced by multiple steps of nanotube dispersion and suspension filtration. Randomly oriented SWNT buckypaper were produced by simple filtering SWNT suspensions after sonification at High performance materials institute(HPMI) in Florida state university. Fig. 1 shows the AFM image of buckypaper surface. The average thickness of buckypaper was 11 μ m and specific gravity was 0.72 g/cm³. Petroleum pitch (M50) used in this paper was supplied by Marathon Co.(USA). Softening point of pitch was 104 ~ 123 °C, specific gravity was 1.22 g/cm³ and sulfur content was 0.5 ~ 4 wt%. The specimen notation is DSC1 (1st carbonized specimen), DSC2 (2nd carbonized specimen), and DSC3 (3rd carbonized specimen).

Figure 1. AFM image of buckypaper surface

Carbonization

The black colored solid pitch was dissolved at 60 °C in toluene to obtain a 25 wt % solution. Buckypaper was dipped into pitch solution for 1 min. at 40 °C. To remove solvent, the dipped buckypaper was put 24 hr at room temperature and 2 hr at 120 °C in oven. The dried specimen was stabilized in nitrogen at 380 °C. Carbonization of pitch was performed in nitrogen at 1000 °C. To increase the contents of carbon matrix from pitch dipping, stabilization and carbonization process was repeated until 3 times. The experimental flow diagram is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Experimental flow diagram

Characterization of carbon/carbon

Density of carbon/carbon samples was obtained according to ASTM D792. Morphologies of the specimen were investigated using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-7401F, JEOL Co.) and element analysis was performed by EDAX. Raman spectra were collected using Renishaw inVia micro-Raman system with excitation wavelength of 785 nm (1.58 eV) from diode laser. Objective lens with magnification of 50 gives spot size smaller than 1 μm and 0.5 mW laser power was used. Electrical conductivity was measured using four-probe method. Keithley 6221 current source and 2182 nanovoltmeter were used for current bias and voltage reading. Buckypaper, DSC1, and DSC2 were pressure contacted using 3 mm equidistance silver wires and DSC3 was contacted using silver-paste and gold wire due to its irregular surface shape. (Current-voltage characteristics show Ohmic behavior and conductivity was estimated from the slope and sample dimension.)

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Morphology and elemental analysis of carbon/carbon composite

Fig. 3 shows SEM images of carbon/carbon composites. At DSC1 (Fig. 3, a) pitch was impregnated and carbonized between nanotubes, but there were several big voids that were efficiently made up in the buckypaper. At DSC2 (Fig. 3, b) and DSC3 (Fig. 3, c), numbers and size of voids were remarkably reduced and void size was nearly within 100 nm. As increase of carbonization, buckypaper was filled with more pitch and numbers and size of voids in carbon/carbon composite was decreased. Decreased voids in carbon/carbon composite will be related to the specimen density.

EDAX was used to analyze the matrix pitch. Fig. 4 shows EDAX graph of carbon/carbon matrix. There were 4 peaks in EDAX result, C, Al, S, Fe. Main constituent was carbon but small amount of Fe was added when making carbon nanotubes as catalyst, sulfur was came from sonicator tip, and aluminum was sample mount for SEM. At this result, we can conclude that carbon atom is main element at matrix with 87.68 wt % and carbonization was completed sufficiently.

Figure 3. Morphology of carbon/carbon composites

Figure 4. EDAX result for carbon/carbon matrix

Density of carbon/carbon composite

Fig. 5 shows density changes of carbonized specimens. Because buckypaper was made up of SWNTs and had membrane shape, buckypaper density was 0.72. After 1st carbonization (DSC1), density was increased up to 2.23 times more than buckypaper. This increase means that pitch was carbonized after impregnation between nanotubes and carbon matrix was formed in the buckypaper. For 2nd carbonization(DSC2), density was still increased up to 2.93 times and saturated. It can be easily explained that several voids at SEM photo of DSC1 is related to low density of DSC1 compare with DSC2 and DSC3 specimens.

Figure 5. Densities of carbon/carbon composites

Electrical conductivity

Major object of this experimental was increment of electrical conductivity after carbonization. Fig. 6 shows the electrical conductivity of carbon/carbon composites. With increase of the number of carbonization times, electrical conductivity was increased and maximum conductivity was obtained at DSC3. This increase can be explained that the vacant space between CNTs in buckypaper was filled and interconnected by carbon from pitch after carbonization and CNT's discontinuity was remarkably overcome. This result will make the buckypaper/pitch carbon/carbon composite as good conducting material as it has a high electrical conductivity.

Figure 6. Electrical conductivity of carbon/carbon composites

Raman spectroscopy

As shown in Fig. 7, Raman spectra of buckypaper/pitch carbon/carbon composites are characterized

by a strong band at approximately 1594 cm^{-1} (G band), a very weak band at approximately 1293 cm^{-1} (D band), and medium band at $234 \sim 267\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (RBM band) [8-9]. All of the carbonized specimen's peaks were decreased at same scale which means carbonization made CNTs from freely state to restricted state. And at CNT's RBM band, small diameter of radial breathing band (267 cm^{-1}) was higher than big diameter (234 cm^{-1}). But after carbonization, the height of small diameter's bands was reduced more than big diameter and the inversion of peak height was occurred between two peaks. From this result we can see that CNTs were safely carbonized without any structure destruction and RBM band of CNTs with small diameter was formerly restricted.

Figure 7. Raman spectroscopy of carbon/carbon composites

CONCLUSIONS

Pitch was impregnated and carbonized with randomly oriented SWNT buckypaper until 3 times and carbon/carbon composite was made. Carbon was filled into the almost vacancy of buckypaper after 2nd and 3rd carbonization process. Density of DSC2 was increased up to 2.93 times higher than buckypaper. Electrical conductivity was increased with the number of carbonization and electrical conductivity of DSC3 was 2.15 times higher than buckypaper.

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